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Physiological and Clinical Nervism from the Classics of Science to the Present Days

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The fruitfulness of biomedical concepts is manifested in the possibility of developing numerous problems that open up a broad perspective allowing the researches to assess physiological and pathological processes. The review of the literature analyzes the ideas of physiological and clinical nervism from the classics of science to the present days. Special attention is paid to the state of modern biomedical science. But in spite of the modern research equipment and new instrumental methods of diagnosis and treatment, there is still no generalizing theory of normal physiological and pathological processes adequate to these methods. Without such a theory, it is impossible to arrange a huge experimental and clinical material into a single system. Meanwhile, it is possible to translate the ideas, principles and concepts into a generalizing theory of normal physiological and pathological processes. This theory could help systematize numerous experimental, clinical and theoretical data based on common principles and form the core of the 21st century biology and medicine paradigm.

Keywords: *generalizing ideas, principles and concepts in biology, physiology and medicine, evolution, recapitulation, dissolution, oxygen and nitrate-nitrite respiration, nitric oxide cycle, superoxide anion radical cycle, nitric oxide, nitrogen dioxide, peroxyxynitrite, NO₂ and OH⁻ radical, generalizing ideas and concepts of pathological states development, physiological and clinical nervism, generalizing theory of normal and pathological processes, new paradigm of the 21st century biology and medicine development.*

«Most of all I'd like to emphasize the significance of the theory. This is especially important to do, because nowadays the scientists are simply terrified by abstract thinking in medicine».

G. Selye (1907–1982)

«The spontaneous accumulation of facts and details, the richest research equipment, ensuring its accumulation lead the research thought away from the general issues of physiology, pathology and medicine, making many researchers slaves of the facts and thus causing the decline of the broad general concepts.»

I.V. Davydovsky (1887-1968)

Introduction At present, there is a huge gap between the possibilities of modern instrumental research methods, diagnosis and treatment and the very theoretical basis that a generalized theory of normal physiological and pathological processes should make. Absence of such a theory is acutely felt at all levels of specialist training. This is primarily due to the fact that a huge amount of experimental and clinical material has been accumulated, which is not just difficult, but already impossible to put into a single system. At present, it is difficult to find universal specialists who could highlight all the necessary material with the proper level of depth. In this regard, more and more textbooks, tutorials and other generalizing books in physiology and pathological physiology are written by large groups of authors. Meanwhile, it is already possible to list ideas, principles and concepts that could be translated into a generalizing theory of normal physiological and pathological processes. This theory could help systematize numerous experimental, clinical and theoretical findings based on common principles and form the core of the 21st century biology and medicine paradigm [1-5].

The fruitfulness of any theoretical concept is manifested in the possibility of experimental development of numerous medical and biological problems, and its strength lies in opening up a broad perspective for analyzing the patterns of both physiological and pathological processes. Ideas about the special dominant role of the nervous system in mammals were expressed much earlier than the nervous system experimental physiology, as a scientific basis for the concept of nervism, was originated [6 - 10]. This concept has passed a long historical path in its development. It is believed that the idea of the reflex principle of the nervous system activity was first advanced by the French philosopher R. Descartes (1596-1650).

In the new era these ideas were developed by the famous German doctor F. Hoffmann (1660-1742), who wrote about the influence of the “nervous system on all changes in a healthy and sick body” [10, 11]. These ideas were also shaped by Dr W. Cullen (1712-1790) from Edinburgh, who considered the nervous system as the source of life, the regulator of all normal and pathological processes [6 - 10]. He formulated and substantiated the “nervous principle”, according to which the nerves act via the brain on all tissues and organs of mammals and other higher organisms [11]. These ideas of the modern epoch scientists were anticipated later by the ideas of R. Virchow (1821-1902), who considered: “It's not life in abnormal conditions, not violation as such that causes illness, on the contrary, illness begins with insufficiency of the regulatory apparatus”. [12-14]. Thus, the relevance and fruitfulness of any theoretical concept is being verified and confirmed at various structural and functional levels for a long time while developing a wide range of biomedical issues until new knowledge is fixed in the scientific consciousness of almost all researchers.

I.M. Sechenov (1829 - 1905) and his ideas, anticipating the achievements of N. Wiener (1894-1964) and L. Bertalanffy (1901-1972). The most important stage of nervism, as the established scientific concept, is connected with the research of I.M. Sechenov [15]. He framed the fundamental law concerning the fact that "according to the mode of origin, acts of conscious and unconscious life are reflexes" [15]. I.M. Sechenov also expressed the idea of automatic regulation in living organisms: "... regulators in the animal body can be only automatic." Even in this statement there has already been the idea of the need for direct and inverse links underlying self-regulation processes. Thus, I.M. Sechenov anticipated the ideas of Norbert Wiener (1894–1964), the founder of cybernetics [16] and L. Bertalanffy, the pioneer of the systematic approach [17, 18], who believed that the principle of self-regulation in living systems (or in an ordered set of interrelated elements) should be in automatically maintained constancy of adjustable parameters, which was a significant addition to the theory of homeostatic regulation (or homeostasis) [19].

S.P. Botkin (1832 - 1889) and his neurogenic theory of pathology. Application of I.M. Sechenov's teachings in the clinical practice allowed S.P. Botkin to formulate a neurogenic theory of pathology based on the idea that disorders of the regulatory nervous apparatus underlie many diseases [20]. His idea correlated with the idea of R. Virchow (1821-1902) concerning the fact that "the disease begins with the regulatory apparatus insufficiency" [16]. The further development of I.M. Sechenov's ideas belongs to S.P. Botkin. According to his theory the organism is a complete system, with the activity directed and regulated by the nervous system. The disease is not something independent. It represents the usual phenomena of life under conditions that are not beneficial to the body. He considered various diseases as a consequence of the normal nerve ratio disruption, which he referred to as "clinical nervism" [20]. Striving for a more accurate understanding of the patient, S.P. Botkin developed the working hypotheses of the pathological process, the majority of them were later confirmed and entered the history and tutorials in pathophysiology.

I.P. Pavlov's ideas (1849 - 1936) on nervism. An important contribution to the development of the "physiological nervism" problems was made by Ivan Petrovich Pavlov, the Nobel laureate in physiology and medicine (1904). He defined nervism as a "physiological direction, seeking to spread the influence of the nervous system to the maximum possible amount of the body's activity" [21]. According to his ideas concerning nervism, the lower parts of the nervous system regulate mainly the internal and vegetative autonomic functions. At the same time, adaptation to changes in environmental properties is carried out with the help of the central nervous system, in which the brain plays a special role [22]. Developing in the 20s of the 21st century the ideas about the trophic function of the nervous system, I.P. Pavlov believed, that each organ is under the triple control of the nerves: functional, causing or interrupting its activity; vascular, regulating the delivery of nutrients by the blood; and trophic, determining the use of these substances by the body [23].

Further development of the above issue strengthened I.P. Pavlov's opinion in presence of special kind nervous influences (the so-called trophic influences) [23, 24]. According to I.P. Pavlov, trophic influences provide the necessary level of metabolism in the tissues and change the activity of the organism depending on its need. Further he developed the idea of three types of the nervous system efferent effects on innervated tissues. Among such influences, Pavlov attributed trigger (the onset of vigorous activity causing muscle contraction and gland secretion), vasomotor (dilation or contraction of the vessels to ensure the necessary level of blood circulation), and trophic influences (direct regulation of metabolic nerves in the tissue) [23 - 27].

In contrast to the "clinical nervism" of S.P. Botkin, I.P. Pavlov, as mentioned above, substantiated the concept of "physiological nervism by V.M. Bekhterev (1857 - 1927): according to him the brain plays a leading role in the regulation of body functions. Considering aspects of the mental activity of the individual in the norm and pathology and on their verge, V.M. Bekhterev distributed a complex of the reflexological approach to the study of personality.

Analysing the brain function in the experiment in a healthy and sick person, V.M. Bekhterev came to the conclusion that the brain plays a leading role in the regulation of the body functions. In his articles he wrote: "there is not a single subjective phenomenon, which was not accompanied by objective processes in the brain in the form of a current running through nerve cells and fibers, which is a physical and chemical process" Following I.M. Sechenov, V.M. Bekhterev asserted that "the so-called mental phenomena are reflexes" [28].

L.A. Orbeli (1882 - 1958) and his theory concerning the adaptive-trophic role of the nervous system.

I.P. Pavlov's ideas were further developed in the research of Leon Abgarovitch Orbeli, who proved that irritation of the sympathetic nerves relieves fatigue of the skeletal muscle and restores its effectiveness [29, 30]. So, for the first time L.A. Orbeli established the adaptation-trophic role of the nervous system, the essence of which is that the sympathetic nervous system can change the functional activity of the organs in accordance with the living conditions of the organism [30].

L.A. Orbeli considered the nervous system is involved not only in the regulation of movement and release of hormones from the endocrine glands, but also influences the regulatory nature (adaptation-trophic), which changes the functional properties of the innervated structure.

The adaptive-trophic function of the nervous system maintains the homeostasis of the organism through biochemical changes that occur under the influence of impulses travelling along the sympathetic nerves directly to the organs. The organs without sympathetic innervation do not lose their inherent function, but become more vulnerable and under certain conditions are not able to rearrange the level of metabolism [30].

L.A. Orbeli: denervation returns the tissue to the earlier stage of development, when the tissue or organ reacted directly to the chemical agents. For a long time, physiologists have used nerve transection to study the role of the nervous system on the organ activity

[25, 26]. These studies were necessary not only to understand how the denervated organ works, but also to find answers for practical medicine when injuries and traumas caused damage to the nerve trunks, which further resulted in denervated limbs or muscles.

In the course of research, it was discovered that when the nerve fibers are cut or damaged, the properties of the cells innervated by them change. This concerns both the properties of the surface membrane, biochemical processes in the cytoplasm and intracellular structures (e.g. mitochondria), which, in turn, can lead either to the restoration of an organ or to profound disturbances of organs and tissues (e.g. trophic ulcers) [25, 26]. Analyzing the problem of denervation it is necessary to mark that the achievements of L.A. Orbeli are of great importance, as they were a continuation of his research in the identification of the sympathetic nervous system trophic function. For Orbeli, the sympathetic nervous system was a trophic apparatus, universal for all organs of a living organism, on which depends the adaptation of their activities to given conditions. His conclusions were based on the evolutionary theory and contained the ideas of the function analysis in the process of their phylogenetic study [29]. According to L.A. Orbeli, denervation as it returns the tissue to an earlier stage of development, when the tissue or organ reacted directly to chemical agents [26]. The Kennon-Rosenbluet's denervation law and the ideas on the mechanisms of the denervated tissues sensitivity increase, developed by L.A. Orbeli were logically interconnected and well complemented each other [30–32]. They also agreed well with the research concerning transection of sympathetic or parasympathetic nerves.

The phenomenon of denervated hypersensitivity by W. Kennon (1871-1945).

Cutting sympathetic or parasympathetic nerves, innervating vascular smooth muscles after 5-30 sec. leads to their maximum expansion. However, within a few minutes, hours, days, or weeks, the vascular smooth muscle's own tone increases: an increase in it's contraction is associated not only with sympathetic stimulation, but also with chemical adaptations in the smooth muscle fibers themselves. This occurs due to the fact that an organ without sympathetic or parasympathetic innervation becomes more sensitive to the physiological concentrations of norepinephrine and acetylcholine — the so called phenomenon of denervated hypersensitivity, first discovered by Walter Kennon [31, 32].

After William Kennon's death, Arturo Rosenbluet extended his research and completed the book on denervated hypersensitivity. This book was translated into Russian and published in 1951 under the title "Sensitization of Denervated Structures" [31]. Thus, W. Kennon and A. Rosenblyut, on the basis of their experiments, formulated a law according to which denervated structures increase their sensitivity to the effect of chemical stimuli, being maximal in the directly denervated regions. The reason for the increase in sensitivity, according to the authors, may be because of the fact that nerves carrying impulses to the tissues, have a permanent inhibitory effect on them under normal conditions.

Thus, after transection (and / or rebirth) of sympathetic or parasympathetic nerves, the sensitivity of denervated organs to corresponding mediators increases

dramatically: the organ devoid of sympathetic innervation is particularly sensitive to noradrenaline and adrenaline, and in case it is devoid of parasympathetic innervation it becomes sensitive to acetylcholine. Later it was proved that in case of norepinephrine or acetylcholine release termination in the synapses, the number of receptors in the postsynaptic membranes of the effector cells sharply increases. This process is called "up-regulation" of receptors. As a result of this phenomenon, the effector reaction is many times magnified in response to the effects of hormones and mediators [31, 32].

General Theory of Pathological Processes by A.D. Speransky (1887/1888 - 1961).

Speransky, Alexey Dmitrievich entered the history of biology and medicine as one of the founders of the general theory of pathological processes [33]. Summarizing numerous data of experimental and clinical studies, he put forward the concept according to which the disturbance of the nervous system trophic function underlies the development of pathological processes. The basis for such a conclusion was the numerous experimental and clinical data and the findings concerning the regulatory effects of the nervous system on organs and tissues and their association with the impact on the biochemical intracellular processes. According to the ideas of A.D. Speransky the nervous system allows the organs and tissues not only to perform their inherent functions, but also maintains the safety of their structure.

These ideas and the very concept developed by A.D. Speransky are currently known as the "doctrine of the nervous trophism and nerve dystrophies" [25, 26, 33, 34]. Numerous clinical and experimental observations made it possible to consider that the trophic function to some extent is carried out by all nerves and that the specific trophic nerves in the body are few. For example, sympathetic nerves innervating the heart muscle and adipose tissue are referred to them. The trophic effect of the heart sympathetic nerves is manifested in metabolism stimulation in the myocardium, due to accelerated and intensified contractions of the automatically working cardiac muscle and the increased heart excitation rate. Sympathetic trophic nerves of adipose tissue are involved in the mobilization of fat reserves in case of the body's increasing energy needs. A.D. Speransky saw his main task in identifying and substantiating the general patterns of the pathological processes development, which he found to be in close relationship with normal physiology. The results of numerous studies and clinical data showed that the nervous system normally provides not only the performance by organs and tissues their characteristic functions, but also maintains the integrity of their structure. Unlike his teacher - I.P. Pavlov — A.D. Speransky extended the trophic function effect to the entire nervous system, not only to individual "trophic nerves." Further his point of view significantly changed the initial I.P. Pavlov's concept concerning nervism and "trophic innervation."

A.D. Speransky: all diseases are associated with the trophic function of the nervous system, its violation is accompanied by neuro-dystrophic processes preceding the manifestations of the disease [33, 278].

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A.D. Speransky's ideas entered the history of medicine as "the research of nervous trophism and nervous dystrophy." The above provisions are included in his main book "Elements of the Medical Theory Construction" published for the first time in 1935 [33]. In the process of this book writing, A. D. Speransky pondered a lot on the methodological problems of the general pathology development, understanding the need for a creative collaboration with physiologists. In search of the optimal forms of such a community, he participated in the project of the new scientific institution creation with the structure ensuring closer interaction between experimenters and clinicians of different profiles in solving urgent issues of biology and medicine. For such a purpose the All-Union Institute of Experimental Medicine (AUIEM) was set up in 1932.

Scientific and organizational activities of Academician A.D. Speransky. The main task of a newly created Institute was comprehensive study of the human body, search for new methods of treatment and prevention of diseases. A.D. Speransky headed the Institute Department of General Pathology, which later became the largest school of Soviet pathologists. Despite the official recognition of A.D. Speransky and his election an Academician in 1939, the scientific medical community met his ideas ambiguously. On the one hand, many scientists and doctors sought to get into the school of A.D. Speransky, but on the other hand, a number of scientists, physiologists and pathologists brought up on the ideas of Fervorn's Cellular Physiology (1863–1921) and Virchow's Cellular Pathology (1821-1902) did not agree with the new understanding of the nervous system role in the development of pathological processes [34]. In addition, the experimental verification of his ideas were not always successful, which caused a critical attitude towards them. This happened due to the methodological level of research in the 40s – 60s of the 20th century.

The emergence of new research methods, allowing the scientists to study the metabolic changes in tissues and body fluids, the activity of energy processes, confirmed the findings of A.D. Speransky. At present, physiology, pathophysiology, neurophysiology, neurochemistry, and neuromorphology have convincing evidence of the fine mechanisms of neurotrophic influences.

Such phenomena as the interrelation of intracellular processes with the intensity of energy production in mitochondria [35], protein synthesis with the intensity of specific cell functions, as well as the involvement of the nervous system in the regulation of these processes were discovered. The role of various brain neurotransmitter systems in the process of its integrative activity in normal conditions and in the neuro-dystrophic process has been studied [25, 26].

New data on the regulatory peptides formation both in the central nervous system (CNS) and in other organs and tissues including the findings concerning their participation in normal physiological processes [36] appeared. Their polyfunctionality was also discovered (a regulatory role in the normal physiological state and a protective role in various pathological conditions, including brain injuries) [37, 38].

Currently, no one doubts the correctness of A.D. Speransky's ideas on the nervous system trophic function, with its effect on the innervated organs and tissues

realized through physical and chemical processes providing their normal structure and function. In the same way, associations are established between nerve cells and within the central nervous system itself. Hence, the damage caused to individual links of these processes must be accompanied by violations of the specific functions of organs and tissues, which was implied by A.D. Speransky under the term neuro-dystrophic process.

In 1944 the USSR Academy of Medical Sciences was established. A.D. Speransky took an active part in its organization and was among the first elected Full Members of the USSR Academy of Medical Sciences. The Department of General Pathology headed by him at AUIEM was transformed into the Institute of General and Experimental Pathology of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the USSR, and A.D. Speransky became its first Director.

In the 50-60 years of the 20th century A.D. Speransky conducted a large cycle of research on three main problems: "infection and disease", "disease and recovery", "recovery and treatment". Clinicians along with the institute staff participated in the research of these problems. The obtained results were summarized in 5 Collections of Works published in the 50s when A.D. Speransky was still alive, though the findings of the above studies were not summarized and arranged by him in a separate book due to his death in July 23, 1961.

Later, for several months, the Group of A.D. Speransky was led by M.G. Durmishyan (1910 - 1961), who, transferred this Group to 33 Bolshaya Kaluzhskaya, (now 33 Leninsky Prospect) with the support of E.A. Asratyan (1903 - 1981) where his Physiological Laboratory attached to the USSR Academy of Sciences was located.

In some time, thanks to the support and advice of E.A. Asratyan, the Academician A.D. Speransky's Group of Individual Research was renamed into the Laboratory of the Nervous System Trophic Function, which became a part of the Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of the USSR Academy of Sciences. After the death of M.G. Durmishyan at the end of 1961 Ya. I. Azhipa became the Head of the Laboratory (1924 – 1992).

The views and ideas of A.D. Speransky entered the history of medicine and numerous medical encyclopedias attracting the attention of many biologists, medical researchers and practical doctors in many countries around the world. His teachings in Russia were continued by Ya.I. Azhipa (1924 - 1992) [25, 26], V.A. Govyrin (1924 - 1994) [39 - 41], V.N. Shvaley (r.1929) [42 - 44], O.V. Volkova [161], and D.M. Golub (1901–2001) in Belarus [45-47].

Ya.I. Azhipa (1924-1992) and his colleagues found out that in the process of neuro-dystrophic development the nerves of the endocrine glands can affect not only the sensitivity of the endocrine glands to specific humoral factors, but also to many physiological and biochemical parameters, including energy processes in individual organs [48] and the content of secondary mediators, particularly cAMP [25, 26, 48]. Thus Ya.I. Azhipa has experimentally proved the adaptive-trophic effect of the nerves of the endocrine glands and mediators on physiological and biochemical processes. He summarized the

data of experimental and clinical studies obtained during the 80ies of the 20th century in his two monographs [25, 26].

V.A. Govyrin (1924-1994). Transfer of sympathetic effects on the tissue is carried out with the participation of the vascular nerves, which emit mediator noradrenaline with their endings. This mediator reaches the cells by means of diffusion [39 - 41]. Sympathetic effects, having a functional nature, are manifested in the narrowing and relaxation of blood vessels, increase in strength and heart rate. The loss of trophic effects of functional nerves is revealed, for example, in atrophy of skeletal muscles, lacking motor innervation. After transection of the motor nerve, the volume of muscle cells decreases, the function of the contractile apparatus is disturbed, and the metabolism changes significantly. After ingrowth of the cut nerve into the muscle, its structure and function gradually restore. D.M. Golub, the Belarusian scientist [45 - 47] devoted his research to the issues of the developing organs interaction with the nerves growing within them.

D.M. Golub (1901 - 2001): after the ingrowth of the cut nerve into various organs, the structure and function of the latter are gradually restored. During the WW2 in front of clinical neurologists arose the problem of rehabilitation of wounded patients with peripheral nervous system injuries. D.M. Golub conducted experimental studies examining the possibilities of nerve restoration in case of their large defects [45].

In the course of his studies, the data, obtained in 1933 to 1940 were used. It was at that time when he discovered that the developing organs effectively interact with the nerves growing within them [46]. In the postwar years (1945–1970) the main attention of D.M. Golub and his colleagues was focused on the embryology of the peripheral nervous system, especially on the autonomic one [47].

Studies of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems embryogenesis dynamics revealed three stages in the development of the sympathetic stem: the primary segmentation stage, the primary nodal stage fusion into a continuous nerve cell cord and the definitive nodule formation stage [45 - 47]. The main focus D.M. Golub drew on the second stage. It is at this stage that the cellular and fibrous elements move with the simultaneous formation of multi-segment definitive nodes. Due to this phenomenon, satellite nodes appear around large vegetative ganglia, which further participate in the development of compensatory-adaptive reactions involving the autonomic nervous system. D.M. Golub proved that the final stage in the vegetative nodes formation, both sympathetic and parasympathetic, is always dispersion of a part of young nerve cells from definitive nodes. As a result of this process, additional microganglia appear close to the main ganglion, connected with the main node by the bundles of nerve fibers.

P.A. Motavkin: neuroendocrine and intimal mechanisms of hemodynamic control in brain vessels [6.7]. In the early 70s of the previous century, P.A. Motavkin's histochemical works on choline and adrenergic innervation of the brain vessels began to appear in domestic and foreign journals.[49 - 51]. In the 80s, the neurohistological school of P.A. Motavkin has become on a par with such well-known and recognized research-

ers of the neurochemical organization of the autonomic plexuses of brain vessels such as Nielse, Edvinsson, Owma, Olsen (Lund, Sweden). As a result of many years of research undertaken by researchers and resident students of the Department of Histology, Vladivostok Medical University, extensive and convincing data were obtained allowing them to isolate the brain and intramedullary branches of the autonomic nervous system, attribute to it the paravascular nerves and ganglia nerve cells forming functional connections with the blood vessels and ependyma shell. It has been proved that the intracerebral part of the autonomic nervous system innervates the intraorganic blood vessels, paravascular connective tissue, glial membranes and the ependymal membrane [49-54].

All of them provide the vital activity of neurons and form an auxiliary apparatus of the brain, which has innervation similar to somatic organs. It has been established that the intramedullary part is not isolated from the nervous apparatus of the great cerebral vessels, on the contrary, they act as a whole. This gave reason to consider them in unity as branches with the common bases of organization. Thus, the scope of the main scientific interests of P.A. Motavkin, his colleagues and students became the research of the hemodynamics control mechanisms in the brain vessels or intimate and neuroendocrine regulation mechanisms.

Studying ontogenesis and ultrastructure of brain capillaries, P.A. Motavkin proposed a new concept, according to which the constriction and vascular relaxation mechanisms are spatially separated; he established a direct and reverse interaction between the capillary and the neuron in the realization of the nervous system trophic function.

Thanks to P.A. Motavkin's and his students' research the theory on the management of cerebral hemodynamics, including the mechanisms associated with NO and its transformation products was developed. Their research is of great significance for further understanding of how normal, physiological hemodynamics becomes pathological. With every year they are becoming increasingly important because they lay the foundation for further research of many processes activated in case of the disturbed nervous system trophic function, cerebral circulation, ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes [55 - 68].

Development of the V.A. Govyrin's concept, according to which the transfer of sympathetic influences on the tissue is carried out with the participation of vascular nerves, releasing mediator noradrenaline with their endings. It is known, that norepinephrine, secreted by the vascular nerves, reaches the cells by diffusion [39 - 41]. Sympathetic effects, which externally have a functional character, as mentioned above, are manifested in the contraction and relaxation of blood vessels, an increase in strength and heart rate. On the material of early autopsies (after sudden death and victims killed in accidents) using neurohistochemical methods V.N. Shvaley and his colleagues proved that even prior to the development of obvious atherosclerotic changes, the vascular wall in places of vascular branching undergoes changes expressed in a decrease of adrenergic nerve plexuses average total density [42 - 44]. In addition, the phenomena of deafferentation were not-

ed in the areas of the vascular wall predisposed to atherosclerosis.

In particular, a significant decrease in the number of baroreceptors - encapsulated sensory nerve endings — was discovered, which is normally a sign of intravascular pressure. However, studies have shown that the process of the vessel wall desympathization and the violation of its nervous trophism precede the development of its atherosclerotic changes [42 - 44]. What could be their causes? To answer this question, V.N. Shvalev turned to the author of this review, who, together with his colleagues [69 - 99], previously received experimental data, which were part of the concept [1-5, 100- 118], and which could shed light to the above issue.

Antioxidant and antiradical activity of sympathetic nervous system mediators. Literature data evidenced that norepinephrine and adrenaline belong to biophenols, which contain a closed system of delocalized π - electrons in the aromatic ring and an OH group capable of detaching a hydrogen atom (H) and forming a phenoxyl radical [119]. The aromatic ring with a system of delocalized electrons makes it relatively easy to receive and release electrons and, thus, to participate in antiradical and antioxidant reactions.

In this regard, as long as the sympathetic nervous system is capable of producing and releasing norepinephrine and adrenaline, tissues (e.g. vascular intima), in which nerve endings are located, will be protected from oxidative and nitrosative stress. This is one of the most important, but little studied by physiologists, properties of the sympathetic nervous system and its neurotransmitters. Inactivation of catecholamines (noradrenaline, dopamine) occurs by oxidative desamination using FAD-dependent enzyme monoamine oxidase (MAO).

The formation and disintegration of catecholamines, when considered from the point of view of the cyclicality principle, is analogous to cell cycles or the life cycle of some individuals. Therefore, they can be qualified as peculiar catecholamine cycles. The resulting oxidized forms (the corresponding aldehydes or acids) are soluble in water and excreted by the kidneys. Adrenaline is inactivated by the methylation of a hydroxyl group involving adrenalmethyltransferase. The resulting methylarginine enters the liver, where it is conjugated with glucuronic or sulfuric acid and then excreted [120].

Thus, the literature data concerning the fact that noradrenaline and adrenaline belong to biophenols, containing a closed system of delocalized π - electrons in an aromatic ring and an OH group capable of detaching a hydrogen atom (H) and forming a phenoxyl radical [119], give reason to assume presence of antioxidant and antiradical properties of these mediators.

A new concept: Protection of blood vessel cells with the participation of vegetative nervous system mediators is able to prevent the development of the neuro-dystrophic process in blood vessels, formation of atherosclerotic plaques and reduce the likelihood of myocardial infarction, ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes. Currently the available experimental and clinical data allow us to conclude that protection of blood vessel cells with the participation of vegetative nervous system mediators can prevent the development of the neuro-dystrophic process in blood vessels, formation of atherosclerotic plaques and reduce the likelihood of my-

ocardial infarction, ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes. [42-43, 67, 118]. This concept is in good agreement with the modern understanding of the "disease", according to which the molecular mechanisms of the pathology development are contained in the body, leading (in combination with environmental factors or independently) to the development of a disease.

This concept is also in agreement with many theories of pathology including the theory of R. Virchow's cells pathology [10, 12-14], A.D. Speransky's theory on neuro-dystrophic processes [9, 10, 25, 26, 33], the theory of adaptation violation through the general adaptation syndrome (GAS), distress development [128, 129], etc. And finally, this concept well complements the existing ideas about the formation of atherosclerotic plaques, since the mechanism of the lipid formations in newborns and children of the first year of life [160] without this concept remained unclear [5, 67, 118].

In this regard, the proposed concept can be not only an addition to the existing theories of atherosclerotic plaque formation and vascular damage during infarction, ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke, but also serve as a basis for the formation of the general theory elements of the physiological and pathological processes [1].

A new concept on the protective role of the sympathetic nervous system mediators in blood vessels from free-radical nitrogen and oxygen compounds and its role in explaining the mechanisms of numerous pathological processes development. The concept "common denominator" concerning the protective role of the vegetative nervous system (VNS) sympathetic division from free-radical compounds, proposed by us [67], is as follows: development of many pathological processes is based on disturbances in the cycles of nitric oxide [100-107] and a superoxide anion radical [102] leading to the formation of an increased content of nitrogen dioxide ($\cdot\text{NO}_2$), the strongest oxidizer with high reactivity [117, 118, 121, 122]. Increased formation of $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ occurs during any hypoxic/ischemic processes, including intrauterine hypoxia / ischemia, followed by reoxygenation, when the body switches from oxygen respiration to more ancient nitrate-nitrite respiration with further return to oxygen respiration [3, 123, 124].

Activation of $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ formation takes place in autoimmune diseases, inflammatory processes, traumatic injuries, cardiovascular diseases involving the appearance of atherosclerotic plaques and local damage to blood vessels further leading to heart attacks, ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes [118, 150]. Increased formation of $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ occurs in cancer and injuries, including brain injury. Thus, one of the essential generalizations is as follows: **numerous pathological processes as common denominators contain a common component — increased formation of $\cdot\text{NO}_2$, as a result of nitric oxide and the superoxide anion radical cycles disturbance which occur due to oxygen and nitrate-nitrite respiration failure** [126, 127]. Practically it is difficult to find at least one of the 10,000 nosological forms available in the modern nomenclature and classification of diseases, injuries and causes of death, which would not be accompanied by an increased production of $\cdot\text{NO}_2$ resulting from the violation of nitric oxide cycles and superoxide anion radical.

One of the most striking manifestations of such processes in the development of numerous pathologies is free-radical nitration of tyrosine and the formation of nitrotyrosine. It is possible to say that numerous pathological processes, being a common denominator, contain a general component – increased formation of NO_2 , due to violation of nitric oxide and a superoxide anion-radical cycles, and arising from the failure of oxygen and nitrate-nitrite respiration mechanisms.

Thus, ontogenesis repeats phylogenesis, and the individual history of the body's illness is a reflection of phylogenesis – the anamnesis of all living beings associated with the transition from oxygen respiration to nitrate nitrite respiration with subsequent return to oxygen respiration or the death of the organism [3, 126, 127].

This position is consistent with the ideas of evolution, recapitulation and dissolution [3]. Earlier, discussing the presence of evolutionary ancient nitrate-nitrite respiration and evolutionary younger oxygen respiration in living organisms, we repeatedly pointed out that Nature never refuses once successfully found solutions [136].

The only problem was why is this happening? Analysis of the conflict between nitrate-nitrite and oxygen respiration from the standpoint of the classical concepts of evolution, recapitulation and dissolution led us to the conclusion that this is due to the following circumstances: in living organisms, there is a subordination of biochemical and physiological mechanisms.

Evolutionary mechanisms formed at the late stages of phylogenesis cannot cancel the effect of earlier mechanisms. With small deviations from the norm, nitrate-nitrite respiration is capable, under conditions of oxygen starvation (hypoxia), to perform the function of a compensatory-adaptive mechanism. However, with deep and prolonged hypoxia or chronic inflammatory processes, oxygenation or re-oxygenation can be fatal.

V.N. Titov independently came to a similar conclusion, but on another occasion, directly related to the development of pathological processes [13]: “Methodological techniques in phylogenesis are the continuity of biological functions, reactions and biological subordination, when humoral mediators developed later in phylogenesis cannot cancel the effect of phylogenetically earlier mediators. The discrepancy between humoral regulation at different stages of phylogenesis, autocrine and paracrine levels, creates the basis and the unity of the pathogenesis of all “metabolic pandemics,” including essential arterial hypertension and insulin resistance syndrome [13].

Returning again to the problem under discussion, related to the reversible transition from evolutionary younger oxygen respiration to ancient nitrate-nitrite respiration, it can be added that in the above conditions due to endogenous synthesis, or supply of nitrates and nitrites with water, food products or drugs a fairly high concentration of nitrates, nitrites and nitrogen oxides (NO and NO_2) is formed.

At the same time, the volume of compensatory-adaptive mechanisms decreases. This, in turn, leads to greater vulnerability of almost all groups of the population. Especially in case a person becomes ill or has chronic diseases. Risk groups include pregnant women, people with iron deficiency anemia, and cardiovascular diseases. That is why the nitrate-nitrite background led

only on the territory of the USSR and the CIS countries to a significant reduction in the average life expectancy of the active population [137, 151].

All the above mentioned affected the number of the population in a liberal-democratic Russia, the 3rd fold increase in mortality from cardiovascular diseases and doubling of deaths cases from cancer [137]. The main cause of all these phenomena can be a conflict between the above 2 types of respiration [136], a violation of the cyclic mechanisms of nitrogen and oxygen reactive forms regulation [124], nitrosative and oxidative stress [123, 124], aggravated by the additional intake of oxygen into the blood during reoxygenation against the background of a high concentration of nitrates and nitrites capable of transforming into NO and NO_2 .

Thus, oxygenation / reoxygenation under these conditions can significantly increase the concentration of highly reactive compounds, nitrogen dioxide and peroxynitrites, able to re-release NO_2 and OH radicals. Hence, at the level of a living organism, a conflict occurs between an evolutionarily more ancient mechanism of nitrate-nitrite respiration and an evolutionarily younger oxygen respiration.

The appearance of NO_2 leads to DNA guanine bases damage [73, 74], which can be completed with single and double-stranded DNA breaks, chromosomal aberrations, leading to impaired interaction between cells, including the violation of contact inhibition, when individual cells do not care ‘what happens to the neighboring cells’ as is in case with the transformation of normal cells into malignant ones.

Sometimes these phenomena are described by William Shakespeare’s words: “the connection of times was broken” or “the connecting thread broke” between subcellular structures, cells, tissues and organs. Such phenomena, as a rule, occur in numerous pathological processes, including cardiovascular diseases and tumor growth. So, the ideas we develop are in good agreement with other known definitions of pathological processes and a disease [138–140].

It is about them many scientists say that the inconsistency of regulation at different stages of phylogenesis at different structural and functional levels is the basis and unity of many pathological processes [138–141]. Moreover, the development of pathological processes begins with the violation and damage of evolutionary young structures, functions and mechanisms while preserving the evolutionarily more ancient ones.

The statements we develop correspond to the classical concepts of evolution, recapitulation, and dissolution [3]. Besides, they are well consistent not only with the basic ideas, principles and concepts of physiological and clinical nervalism, but also with almost all main theories of pathology developed from the classics of science to our days providing answers to a number of issues that remained unresolved for a long time, for about 2000 years.

According to the teachings of ancient scientists and doctors development of pathology is the transition from harmony to disharmony between substances and their components; in accordance with the humoral theories by Hippocrates and Rokitsky, in the imbalance - dyscrasias, and in accordance with the theory by R. Virchow, pathology always occurs against the background of the disturbance of regulatory processes in the cells. From

our point of view, behind all these processes, there are normal cyclic regulatory processes that ensure the concentration of blood cells and physiologically active substances in the blood and tissues of the body within the physiological norm.

Since all regulatory processes imply the presence of closed feedback (the signal from the exit goes to the entrance), cyclic and periodic processes are the foundation of all normal physiological processes, and their disruption leads to the onset of the pathological processes development.

Our concepts are in good agreement with the ideas followed by L.A. Orbeli: "we have little reckoning with the fact that each physiological process is cyclic, and has its own cyclicity". Our concept is also agrees well with the ideas of nervism and the theory of the neuro-dystrophic process by A.D. Speransky, which accompanies many pathological processes, including those associated with space weather and the nitrate-nitrite background of modern man existence [162, 163,]. The above questions and the answers to them can be found in the literature cited by us [1–5, 35–38, 42–44, 56–118, 121–127, 131–134, 164, 165, 177–180] and in publications of the Eurasian Scientific Association [2 - 4, 123, 124, 147.148, 150–159, 166–176].

Conclusion. Systematization of experimental, clinical data and theoretical generalizations based on common principles that can form the core of the XXI century biology and medicine paradigm. At present, the atomic principle of the matter structure has become an integral part of almost all theories, concepts and views in biology and medicine. Maintaining the concentration of chemical / biochemical compounds or physiologically active substances within the physiological norm means homeostatic regulation of the living system. Earlier, the classics of science indicated that the nervous system and the VNS, in particular, provides regulation of body systems at various structural and functional levels and ensures the maintenance of homeostasis.

Currently, the concept of homeostasis is in many ways far from complete. From a mathematical point of view, as mentioned above, homeostasis has long been well described, but its essence remains unknown to many scientists so far.

On this occasion, A. Poincaré wrote: "... to a certain extent, any generalization implies belief in the unity and simplicity of Nature. As for unity, we will not be able to

meet any difficulties here ... We need to ask a question not about whether Nature is unified, but how it is unified? "In previous works we expressed our point of view that the essence of homeostasis is one of the global principles - the principle of cyclicity-, which subordinates the molecular, biochemical and physiological systems at almost all structural and functional levels, the principle that is able to become on a par with the atomic principle of a substance structure.

Physiologists and pathophysiologicalists know, in order to find out how important this or that structure or function in the body, it is enough to turn it off and see what happens. You can invite our readers to conduct an experiment and imagine what happens if you turn off all cyclic (or periodic) processes. It's clear, that all biological rhythms, including periodic processes in the brain and heart, will disappear. At the same time, hemoglobin will cease to give and attach oxygen, blood circulation will stop, all pumps that pump out some ions and other cells into the tissue will stop, the heart will stop working. Naturally, all enzymes work of which is carried out in a cyclic model will stop working; it means that all energy processes will also stop. If all biological rhythms, cyclic and biochemical processes stop, this will not only lead to the lethal outcome of living organisms, but also to the vanishing of all life on the planet.

All this suggests that cyclic processes play a fundamental role in living organisms, and their violation can be the cause of a variety of diseases, including the development of the initial stages of vascular damage leading to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques and violations of the integrity of blood vessels in hemorrhagic strokes.

Moreover, the Universe with its spiraling galaxies obeying the principle of cyclicity will not exist, and the Sun and other stars with their nitrogen-carbon Bethe-Weizsäcker cycles will not exist either.

Thus, the principle of cyclicity, according to our ideas, is one of the fundamental principles of living and inanimate matter. However, the degree of its globality or universality remains poorly understood so far.

We believe that the ability of organisms to self-preservation (homeostasis) together with the mechanisms of its maintenance, exist due to this fundamental principle of cyclicity. Thus, it is beyond any doubts, that the important role of VNS is to maintain homeostasis, while homeostasis in its turn maintains all physiological parameters within the physiological norm.

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